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ETHNOPHYSICAL STUDIES ON SALAI JIN DANCE IN NORTH MALUKU AS A SOURCE OF LEARNING PHYSICS

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INTRODUCTION

- Local Wisdom-Based Education
- Ethnophysics as a Physics Learning Resource

Salai Jin Dance of Local Wisdom in North Maluku

image source: <https://www.goodnewsfromindonesia.id/2017/01/24/salai-jin-tradisi-mistis-ternate-hingga-kini>

Salai Jin dance is an ethnic dance originating from Ternate, North Maluku. This dance is a medium of communication with the jinn. The Salai Jin dance is actually a series of activities from traditional rituals that have a high tradition and philosophy for the indigenous people of Ternate.

Long time ago, this dance was used by the ancestors of the Ternate people to communicate with the Jin people who were in the supernatural. The purpose of this communication is to ask for the help of the Jinn to solve various problems faced by humans. One of the problems that most often causes this dance to be held is an illness suffered by a family member.

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RESEARCH METHODS

- This research is included in the qualitative research method in the form of literature study. Through this method, researchers can describe the problems discussed clearly and comprehensively.
- The research method used is descriptive qualitative with data collection techniques through observation, questionnaires and interviews. The data obtained were then analyzed, verified, and reduced then constructed into scientific knowledge and interpreted into physics concepts in class X and XI high school.

RESULT

Local Wisdom-Based Education

Local wisdom-based education is carried out as an effort to introduce the nation's culture to students by implementing it into learning activities, one of which is physics.

Ethnophysics as a Physics Learning Resource

This local wisdom can be used as a means of learning physics called ethnophysics, through this local wisdom interactive learning can occur where there is active interaction between students, educators and the learning resources used.

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Ethnophysics Study of Salai Jin Dance

In the context of ethnophysics, this salai jin dance can be used as a source of physics learning. From the beginning of the Salai Jin dance movement to the end, it can be studied with the concepts of dynamics of motion and rotation in physics for class X and XII SMA/MA.

Dance Phase:

1. Opening Dance

Physics Study:

1. Mechanical Wave
2. Friction

2. Dance Core

Physics Study:

1. Moment of inertia
2. Vertical downward motion

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Ethnophysics Study of Salai Jin Dance

Dance Phase: 3. Dance Core

Physics Study:

1. Newton's Second Law

4. Dance Core

Physics Study:

1. Moment of inertia

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Ethnophysics Study of Salai Jin Dance

Dance Phase:

5. Dance Core

Physics Study:

1. Free Fall Motion (GJB)

6. Closing Dance

Physics Study:

1. Straight Motion Changes Regularly (GLBB)

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DISCUSSION

- Based on the results, that the salai jin dance can be studied with various physical concepts, including the dynamics of motion and rotation along with sound waves. This Salai Jin dance can be used as a source of learning physics based on local wisdom in North Maluku. A learning approach using local wisdom is very important so that students get contextual and meaningful learning (Fuad, 2018). In line with the increasingly globalized times, schools not only carry out cultural transformation of their students but also help in determining the way of life in the future, values and abilities and skills that must be possessed for their future lives. Cultural transformation means changing the form of culture to remain in accordance with an increasingly advanced and complex society by not abandoning the original cultural culture.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results and discussions that have been described, it can be concluded that the Salai Jin dance is a local wisdom in the North Maluku area that can be used as a source of physics learning.

Salai Jin dance can be studied physically with various physics concepts, namely the dynamics of motion and rotation contained in the material for class X and XII SMA/MA.

By using this local wisdom-based learning resource, students can learn physics material as well as foster a love for culture.

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